

Executive plan

Actions for Hackathon Organization & Resources

Translator Recruitment

Finding Translators and reviewers :

- Identify potential translators through academic and professional networks focused on multilingualism.
- Leverage existing communities within OPERAS projects, consortiums, and its cluster to recruit translators and specialists on the languages to be translated.
- Utilize OPERAS National Nodes NL as a resource for identifying translators in various languages.

Also, outreach and incentives:

- Develop communication materials (emails, social media posts) to promote the hackathon and engage translators.

Partner Engagement

Strategic Partnerships:

- Collaborate with OPERAS-affiliated organizations and projects within its cluster to expand outreach and ensure participation of at least 3 specialists per language.
- Engage Atrium partners to enhance the quality, development, visibility and impact of the hackathon.
- Foster partnerships with networks that support multilingualism and open science to ensure alignment with the hackathon's goals.

Organization of a Preliminary Activity: Preparation for the Hackathon

To ensure participants are well-prepared for the Hackathon, a preliminary training session will be organized one week before the main activity. This session aims to equip participants with the necessary skills essential for the activity. On one side, participants will explore the GoTriple platform, gaining an understanding of how the ontology and its associated labels function within the platform's interface—an essential step for ensuring accurate and contextually appropriate translations into other languages. On the other side, participants will be trained to effectively use Mondaecus collaborative translation platform, ensuring they can leverage its features while translating the GoTriple ontology.

Training of Participants

Pre-Hackathon Training Sessions

GoTRIPLE Ontology:

- Organize a preliminary training session (approx. 45 min) to familiarize participants with the GoTriple platform and the functions of the ontology + and the Mondaecus collaborative translation tool.
- Structure training to cover key aspects, including an overview of the ontology, hands-on demonstrations, and Q&A sessions.

Mondaecus translation:

- Conduct a short (20-minute) session for language moderators 1 week or 2–4 days before the hackathon.
- Equip moderators with short guidelines and best practices for maintaining consistency across translations: covering translation, review, and reporting during the workshop.
- Checklists to help participants engage effectively.
- Participants will receive the list of ontology labels and gain access to the **MONDAECUS** platform 3 weeks prior to the hackathon. This early access is intended to allow them to explore the interface, test its features, and prepare for the collaborative workflow, reducing technical uncertainty and enhancing the productivity of the live sessions. The exercise will have the labels list 3 weeks in advance before the hackathon and access to **Mondaecus** 3 weeks in advance.

Objectives:

1. Familiarization with the GoTriple Platform: Participants will be introduced to the GoTriple platform, with a particular focus on its ontology functions. This understanding is crucial for accurately assessing and translating the ontology during the hackathon.
2. Training on Mondaecus: Participants will receive hands-on training on the Mondaecus platform, ensuring they can effectively manage its features and collaborate seamlessly throughout the hackathon.

Structure and Duration:

The preliminary session will last approximately 45 min, with the following stages:

- GoTriple Platform Overview (20 minutes): Introduction to the platform, highlighting the ontology rationale relevant to the translation task.
- Mondaecus Platform Presentation (5 minutes): Overview of the platform's collaborative features and how they support the translation process.

- Mondaecus Interface Walkthrough (10 minutes): A practical demonstration of the platform's interface, ensuring participants can navigate it with ease.
- Q&A Session (10 minutes): Open discussion to address any questions or concerns.

Expected Outcomes:

By the end of the session, participants should:

- Understand how the GoTriple ontology works, including how it defines and labels different content typologies, ensuring accurate and efficient translation into multiple output languages.
- Be competent in using the Mondaecus platform for a collaborative translation exercise.

This preliminary activity is designed to build participants' familiarity with the tools and processes essential for the hackathon. By developing understanding on GoTriple Ontology and clarifying the translation workflow, participants will be able to focus on the core task of translating and reviewing the GoTriple ontology without technical barriers, ultimately enhancing the overall effectiveness and collaborative spirit of the translation.